

LISTADAPT

Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP

Admin details

Project Name LISTADAPT

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Description The Listadapt project aims to decipher the molecular mechanisms of the adaptation of *Listeria monocytogenes* to its various ecological niches by comparing both genotypic and phenotypic data from a large and balanced set of strains from environment, animals, foods and clinical cases in several European countries.

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Version information

Version number

v1.0

Description

This is the initial DMP of EJP OH JRP7 LISTADAPT project

Date of first version

2019/03/29

Date of last update

2019/03/29

1. Data summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose is to collect both genomics and phenotypic data of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains across Europe. The data collection will comply with all national and EU ethics and legal requirements. Access to use these data is needed to address the 4 different LISTADAPT objectives as specified in the grant agreement and summarized below.

- Objective 1: Obtain new knowledge on the genetic basis of the adaptation of *Lm* to different ecological niches
- Objective 2: Generate a database of 4000 genomes using the WGS technology
- Objective 3: Develop and implement new tools for phenotypic analysis
- Objective 4: Make available common resources for European research:
 - 2000 new genomes of *Lm*, deposited in public access internet databases,
 - A molecular database centralizing genes or markers underlying adaptation,
 - A collection well characterized and balanced between strains isolated from food, human, environment and animals.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

The LISTADAPT project generates four different types of data:

- Genomics data of the strains
- Markers of interest (genes, kmers)
- Phenotypic data (Minimal Inhibitory Concentration, growth potential,...)
- Script

The corresponding files formats are respectively:

- .fastq files
- .fasta
- .csv and Rdata files
- .r

Will you re-use any existing data and, if so, how?

The collection of genomics sequences *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from the different compartments will take advantage of existing projects at EU level.

The relevant bioprojects on public repositories associated to that projects are used to collect the relevant genomic fastq files.

What is the origin of the data?

The existing genomics originate from previous and ongoing projects: EFSA LISEQ project (BioProject PRJNA475189), and other recently published projects (PRJEB15123, PRJEB15195, PRJEB22706, and PRJEB15592).

What is the expected size of the data (if known)?

The expected sizes for three of the datasets (markers of interest, phenotypic data, script) is expected to be <1GB.

The size of the collection of genomes is expected to at least a 20GB dataset.

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

The four datasets might be useful for:

- LISTADAPT partners;
- EURL and NRLs for *Listeria monocytogenes*
- EFSA and ECDC
- The scientific community

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?

The dataset of genomes from food compartment is associated to a metadata schema that have been proposed in an EFSA LISEQ project (<https://dx.doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2017.EN-1151>). The metadata of the food strains include more than 10 fields

(Country_code, STs_MLST_Ragon_2008, CCs_MLST_Ragon_2008, Sector, Molecular serotype, Date, EFSA_Complete.MTX.mapping, Food matrix, and Food products).

A specific metadata schema has been initiated for strains isolated from wild/farm animals as well as in environment.

A metadata template is also available for biomarkers of interest for the adaptation of *L. monocytogenes* to different stress conditions.

No specific metadata are yet defined for other datasets (phenotypes and scripts).

Are the data produced and/or used in the project identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism?

The dataset related to genomes have been subdivided in

What naming conventions do you follow?

Naming convention for strains

For naming strains isolated from environment, farm and animals, a naming convention has been adopted.

The naming convention is composed in three levels. The first level is composed of two letters associated to the country of origin:

Country
AT: Austria
FR: France
DK : Denmark
CZ: Czech Republic
IT: Italy
NL : Netherlands
NO : Norway
SE: Sweden
SP: Spain
...

The second and third levels for animals should follow the following naming convention

Level 2 : Animal	Level 3 : Sample type
BOV : Bovine	
PIG : Pig	
AVI : Poultry	
OVI : Ovine	MI: Milk
GOA : Goat	SK: Skin
FIS: Fish	FE: Fecal content
WBO : wild boar	CP: Clinical sample (blood, biopsy, etc.)
DEE : Deer	UN: unknown
FDE: Fallow deer	OT: Other
RDE : Roe deer	
BIR: Birds	
MOO: Moose	
FOX: fox	
OTH: Other	

For farm environment levels 2 and 3 are presented below

Environment	Sample type
FAR: FARM	GL: Grassland /meadow CF: Cultivated field FE: Feed WT: Water through, well used for animal AS: Animal stall UN: Unknown

For soil:

NAT: natural environment	SO: Soil WA: Water VE: Vegetation U: Unknown
URB: Urban	GA: Garden PA: Park

Finally the name of the strains are terminated with a number for helping to distinguish strains that have the same first levels of identification.

The following examples illustrate the naming convention used:

- AT-BOV-MI-1: the strain has been isolated in Austria from milk bovine
- FR-NAT-SO-2: the strain has been isolated in France in soil from natural environment

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No specific keywords have been identified for optimizing possibility of re-use.

What is your approach for clear versioning?

For each datasets, a versioning convention including a number (starting from 1 to n), and the release date (yyyymmdd) is adopted. Examples can be found below:

- Phenotypic data obtained in soil: soilmicrosom_v1_20191028.csv, soilmicrosom_v2_20191230
- Script developed for selecting strains from metadata: metadata2seletion_v1_201904.r

What metadata will be created?

The naming convention used for naming strain corresponds to a metadata schema for strains from animal, farm and environment.

2.2. FAIR data: Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If some data is kept closed provide a rationale for doing so.

At the end of the project any of the four datasets is thought to be made available.

How will the data be made accessible?

The following repositories have been created to made the dataset accessible :

- <https://zenodo.org/record/2617258#.XJ97ZVVKi00> for phenotypic datasets
- <https://github.com/lguillier/LISTADAPT> (other accounts might be added in further version of the DMP)

The Bioproject number for depositiong LISTADAPT genomes is noy yet availabe. An umbargo might be associated to this bioproject.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No specific software are needed to access the data.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited? Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

The repository for script (<https://github.com/lguillier/LISTADAPT>) will be subdivided in different folders corresponding to the different scripts developped.

In the same manner the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/record/2617258#.XJ97ZVVKi00>) will be subdivided in folders corresponding to the different phenotypes.

For genomes, LISTADAPT project might create several Bioproject (one for the different compartments).

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

Some data (genomes, script, phenotype datasets) might be kept under umbergo until publication are finally accepted.

2.3. FAIR data: Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable? What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

LISTADAPT partners will observe OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability, including OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives. These guidelines can be found at: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>.

LISATADAPT partners will also ensure that LISTADAPT datasets observe FAIR data principles under H2020 open-access policy: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-datamgt_en.pdf

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. In specific, information on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodology to follow to facilitate interoperability and whether the project uses standard vocabulary for all data types present to allow interdisciplinary interoperability.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Metadata for the food strains include Foodex2 code.

The metadata associated to the context of isolation of strains from environment and animal might be used to built a specific ontology. Further research are needed to determine if an existing ontology is available.

2.4. FAIR data: Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

[Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) licence as been adopted for the phenotypic and scripts datasets be made available.

When will the data be made available for re-use? If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

Data will only be made available when LISTADAPT partners will release them. Umbargoes will be associated to datasets until the publications from partners that used them will be accepted.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

LISTADAPT is expected to produce data that will be presented to the scientific community, EFSA, ECDC, policy-makers and society at large through a large variety of dissemination actions (communications in scientific conferences, publications...) . Datasets uploaded in the ZENODO, Github and ENA repositories will be freely accessible after an embargo period determined per dataset if required. Potential users are expected to adhere with the Terms of Use of the differents repositories.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on increasing data re-use will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP.

A description of specifications of length of time for which the data will remain re-usable will be provided.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

The quality assurances are not yet described. They might be diiferent according to the LISTADAPT providers of the datasets.

For now, the process of data quality to discover inconsistencies and other anomalies in the data is only used for genomics dataset.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these costs be covered?

The costs for making data FAIR is only related to publication costs (undirect costs). Retained solutions Github, Zenodo and ENA permit to limit theses costs.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Laurent Guilier, project leader of LISTADAPT project, is the responsible of the DMP.

What are the costs and potential value of long term preservation?

No solution for long term preservation have been selected. DRYAD solution (<https://datadryad.org/>) might be chosen for the long term preservation of LISTADAPT datasets.

Further versions of the DMP will takle that points

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

The genomics data are before the creation of the Bioproject are stored on an ANSES server (with a mirror server as a back-up).

Other datasets are stored on servers of LISTADAPT partners. The deliverables will be also saved on EJP OH <https://onehealthjep.eu/> extranet.

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Ethical issues have been reviewed by a specific committee of EJP One Health project.

Legal issues related to the use of strains in LISTADAPT project are taken into account by the systematic signature a Mutual Transfer Agreement.

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

No other procedures are used in LISTADAPT project.